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Peer Learning in Vocational Education and Training – Effects and Changes of Person Relations in Learning Groups

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Abstract

Context: The article focuses on the use of different approaches to peer learning in Vocational Education and Training in Germany.

Approach: Based on a multi-method research study, the question *"How does peer learning influence collaborative learning and social relationships and interactions within classes in the vocational education and training system?"* is researched by using social network analysis and guided interviews.

Findings: The research results show that peer learning, among other things, establishes a positive feedback culture in the learning groups, creates new friendships and makes apprentices want to work more cooperatively with each other in the future. In addition, peer learning was able to promote social integration and solidarity.

Conclusion: These findings make peer learning a potentially meaningful and usable learning approach in Vocational Education and Training.

Keywords: peer learning, person relations, solidarity, feedback culture

1 Introduction

Central criteria for peer learning setting in Vocational Education and Training (VET) are communication at eye level and the reciprocal confidence of the peers. This can facilitate the transfer of skills, competencies and knowledge from peer to peer so that both sides can benefit in the learning process. Therefore, peer learning approaches can be suitable learning methods in VET to increase the learning motivation and learning success of the apprentices. Moreover, it is expected that peer learning, as noted by Topping (1996) and Haag and Streber (2011), among others, improves social learning, contributes to social inclusion and reduces the social isolation of individuals. Peer learning is intended to enable apprentices in VET to become aware that they can achieve more together respectively as a group or a team. Learning together should strengthen the sense of community and promote social integration.

Furthermore, peer learning should help to increase the exchange and feedback among apprentices. Empirical studies such as Kutscha et al. (2012), Gebhardt et al. (2009) and the Training Report of the Federation of German Trade Unions (DGB, 2016) make clear that apprentices would like to receive more feedback and more collegial support as well as more respect and a greater appreciation during their apprenticeship. Moreover, they are sometimes afraid of doing mistakes. There is also the fact that apprenticeship positions remain unfilled in Germany. Maybe because young graduates may prefer a university degree to an apprenticeship so that apprenticeships seem to have potentially decreased in attractiveness in comparison (Struck, 2020).

To overcome these challenges, peer learning can be a useful pedagogical method. This is because peer learning aims to promote mutual feedback as well as praise and appreciation among each other. In practical implementation, apprentices are encouraged, for instance, to ask each other for advice also to address their own uncertainties and their lack of knowledge with other peers. This is supported by the fact that the importance of peer learning for the development of social skills in VET has already been elaborated in an earlier study and the different aspects have been empirically confirmed in the *"Dimensional Model of Social Skills - DMSS"* (Struck & Franz, 2020). In addition, the study by Leijten and Chan (2012) shows that peer learning in VET increases feedback quality and can promote peer feedback strategies as well as increasing interactions between peers. Furthermore, Leijten and Chan (2012) have shown that socially competent behaviour is promoted and that the variety and scope of peer interactions during learning activities have increased.

Nevertheless, there are currently various research desiderata on peer learning, for example, there are only a few empirical studies on informal learning in peer relationships (Krüger & Hoffmann, 2016) as well as on peer relationships in the workplace (Köhler, 2016).

Accordingly, this paper will try to reduce the existing research gap of peer learning in the context of VET. Here will be the focus on the following research question: *"How does peer learning influence collaborative learning and social relationships and interactions within classes in the vocational education and training system?"*

Finally, practical suggestions and hints for the design of learning processes in companies and in VET schools will be formulated.

8 Implementation of the Peer Learning in the Project

At this point, it should be noted that the research question presented and investigated here is part of a larger research project, using some more research methods and focusing on different research questions, which are considered in this article only in part.

In the project, three different forms of peer learning were used: Peer tutoring, peer mentoring and peer education. In peer tutoring, peers are supposed to teach each other. Young learners from the same classes or years (with the same level of information and knowledge) learn and work in tandem in order to repeat, deepen and review vocational or school knowledge together. One person assumes the role of the teacher (or tutor) during the implementation, and the second person the role of the learner. The teacher imparts the knowledge, checks the learner's answers and corrects them if necessary. The other person acts like a learner, which means answering questions, working on given tasks and explaining their own solution.

The two approaches peer education and peer mentoring will be presented together due to numerous similarities in their practical implementation. In both approaches is a group of apprentices, which will be supported by a (different) group of peer educators (from the same apprenticeship year/class) or by peer mentors (from the next higher apprenticeship year/class). The aim is to repeat and consolidate the knowledge that has already been learned. Moreover, the learners are available to answer questions about the content and subject matter (with a low inhibition barrier). In the peer learning approaches, no new content should be covered or learned; rather the (common) goal was an effective and successful preparation for the exams.

9 Theoretical Background

For the theoretical foundation of peer learning, the preliminary considerations of Vygotsky (1929, 1978, 1986) on the internalization of knowledge through social interaction and reciprocal exchange and the considerations of Piaget (1932, 1986) on the importance of the symmetrical peer relationship can take into account. Likewise, the social learning theory of Bandura (1979, 1986) with the idea of learning through model observation and imitation is useful to explain the success of a peer learning approach.

Haag and Streber (2011) point out that peer tutoring enhances prior knowledge and learning strategies, as higher prior knowledge leads to more effective use of learning strategies (Haag & Streber, 2011). In addition, peer tutoring is expected to promote (inter-)active and participatory learning, which facilitates reciprocal feedback and increases responsibility for (one's own) learning process. Moreover, it can and should reduce the social isolation of individuals and (can) have a positive impact on dimensions such as self-esteem, self-confidence and empathy (Topping, 1996).

10 Methods and Results

The effects of peer learning for learning settings in the learning institutions like companies and VET schools in industrial-technical apprenticeships as well as apprenticeships in the healthcare sector in Germany will be analysed by two different research methodological approaches: Social network analysis and guideline-based interviews with apprentices as well as with teachers and instructors. The research setting comprises six schools or companies with a total of 11 classes (243 apprentices). In addition, 39 interviews with apprentices and 15 interviews with teachers and instructors are available for the analysis.

Through such an approach of mixed methods research, the weaknesses of the individual methods should be balanced reciprocally. Thus, as clarified by Steckler et al. (1992), qualitative and quantitative methods are used equally and in parallel in order to be able to analyse the results of each method separately and to verify in a second step whether the results from all methods allow the same (or similar) conclusions. If successful, this approach strengthens the confidence (in the robustness) of the results and conclusions. Furthermore, (single) selected results from the quantitative surveys (results from the social network analysis on the group level) were integrated and validated in the interviews with the apprentices and the teachers/instructors (qualitative methods). Thereby, qualitatively collected data can additionally contribute to an understanding, explanation and interpretation of the quantitative findings (Steckler et al., 1992; Kelle, 2014).

Social network analysis is particularly suitable for illustrating personal relationships in school classes. In this way, both one-way and two-way social relationships can be modelled, and their changes in the networks can be made visible. Following Zander (2014), the working networks and the friendship networks are illustrated and analysed. The surveys are conducted before and after the intervention of peer learning. The algorithm ForceAtlas 2 (Jacomy et al., 2014) was used for the analysis.

Figures 1 and 2 show the results for the question about the working network in a VET school class. The illustration in figure 2 shows an increase in the number of nominations compared to the first measurement. The apprentices in this class named more apprentices they would like to work collaboratively after the peer learning. Thus, new working networks of small groups have (newly) formed; this is made clear by the fact that the apprentices named each other reciprocally.

The illustration in Figures 3 and 4 shows the two measurements for the friendship network question in a VET school class. The modifications between the first and second measurement show an increase in the nominations of other apprentices in the sense of the friendship network. Thus, it can be noted that new friendships have been formed in the VET school class, particularly as a result of apprentices reciprocally nominating each other. It appears that the group as a whole has become closer together during the peer learning project. Likewise, individuals who were previously named less as friends now seem to be more integral part of the class community.

Figure 1 & 2

Results of the Social Network Analysis: Working network - "Whom do you like to work with?", t0 & t1

Figure 3 & 4

Results of the Social Network Analysis: Friendship network - "Who are your best friends?", t0 & t1

The guided interviews with the apprentices are based on Witzel (2000) for a problem-centred interview (PZI) and the analysis was conducted according to a content-structuring qualitative analysis by Kuckartz (2016). The interviews with the teachers and instructors are based on the guidelines of Meuser and Nagel (2002) and Helfferich (2014). The analysis takes into account the suggestions of Meuser and Nagel (2009) and Gläser and Laudel (2010). The analysis of the transcripts was done with the analysis program MAXQDA.

The focus is particularly on perspectives and content-related information on peer learning. The category system was developed both deductively and inductively on the text material. This means that if a (new) text passage does not fit the categories already formed (in terms of content or theme), a new category is formed inductively from the material (Kuckartz, 2016). For further analysis, the coded text passages were also partially paraphrased.

Different aspects were addressed in the interviews, and some statements were coded to the code "reciprocal help of the apprentices", such as: "The other person is happy, you are also happy with yourself, ok he got it now, I have helped him, is great." (male; Original-Speech: „Der andere sich freut, man freut sich auch selber, ok der hats jetzt verstanden, ich hab ihm geholfen, is super.“). Furthermore, statements were identified that suggest that a „positive feedback culture“ has been created, like "Maybe you can add that to the things that I find really positive, that somehow barriers are broken down. The inhibition level drops to ask questions because maybe it's not unpleasant or embarrassing or anything like that. Or you don't have to be ashamed or anything." (female; Original-Speech: „Das kann man vielleicht noch hinzufügen

zu den Sachen, die ich wirklich positiv finde, (.) das halt irgendwie auch so Barrieren abgebaut werden. Halt die Hemmschwelle sinkt, (.) mal Fragen zu stellen, weils einem vielleicht auch nicht unangenehm is (.) oder peinlich (.) oder so ne. Oder man sich nicht da irgendwie schämen muss oder so.“). Although aspects such as „solidarity“ were also clearly addressed, *“So really, we said, “We will do it all together! And if something comes up, we'll help each other.” So nobody gets left behind anymore.”* (male; Original-Speech: *„Also wirklich, wir haben gesagt: „Wir schaffen das alle! Und wenn was ist, helfen wir uns auch mal gegenseitig.“ Also es wurde halt keiner mehr zurückgelassen.“*).

11 Classification of the Results

While the results of the social network analysis illustrate the strengthening or increase in the friendship networks as well as the working networks through peer learning, the results from the interviews with the apprentices and the teaching and instructing staff were able to clarify and exemplify these findings once again. For example, it is possible to see that peer learning creates or can create a positive feedback culture in the classes and learning groups. The apprentices recognize that it can be meaningful and valuable for them to help each other even after the end of the project and to support each other with (appreciative) feedback. Through learning together, they notice that they can trust each other and ask each other for advice. This also explains why they are interested in increased working cooperation (in the future).

Solidarity was also positively experienced and described within peer learning. According to this, peer learning (at least for some apprentices) encourages reflection in a sense of solidarity, recognizing one's own advantages and possibilities. In the interviews, the apprentices describe situations and events from which it becomes clear that they show consideration for lower-performing apprentices, consciously support them in working together as well as in learning together, and thus integrate them into the social community of the class. Accordingly, peer learning (and especially peer tutoring) can contribute to social integration, as previously described by Topping (1996) as well as by Haag and Streber (2011).

The integration of (all) classmates and colleagues into the social (class) community, i.e. the promotion of social integration. The sharing or the renunciation of (one's own) advantage for the benefit of others are also central characteristics of social coexistence, which accordingly (can) also improve the everyday professional working life in teams. VET should also communicate these "values" or perspectives and skills to apprentices, as they are relevant for their later professional behaviour. If it is or can be possible to promote such dimensions in VET, e.g. through peer learning, these pedagogical approaches should be implemented accordingly in the learning locations of the companies and the VET schools.

12 Discussion

Overall, it should be noted that peer learning creates new forms and possibilities of communicative exchange for the apprentices without having to fear sanctions or assessments by the teaching or instructing staff. This creates a protected communicative space in which the feedback culture referred by the apprentices could be developed. The results of the social network analysis, according to which friendship networks and working networks, in particular, have become stronger. Peer learning creates an additional exchange in learning, and the apprentices learn to perceive and understand each other better. From the interviews, it is also clear that the apprentices were able to strengthen their trust among themselves and therefore the networks became closer. As a result, several apprentices experienced themselves effectively and showed solidarity behaviour.

On the other hand, the overall evaluation (in the larger research project) also shows that peer learning does not have an equally or uniformly positive effect on all apprentices. This can be explained by site-specific conditions in the different learning settings. The special features

of the respective learning locations, the six different institutions and the different occupations must be taken into account accordingly when interpreting the results.

However, peer learning in VET must not be "exploited" economically in the future, e.g. in the sense that peer learning must not be used to justify savings in personnel capacity among teaching and instructing staff. Peer learning does not seek to replace teaching or instructing staff, nor should peer learning in VET schools be the answer to teaching shortages. Peer learning should always be seen as a useful addition and used to offer apprentices additional stimulation and learning opportunities so that they can develop and learn together in a trustful setting. In this way, it should be underlined that the learning group can be strengthened from within and that the apprentices (can) recognize that they can achieve more through solidarity, mutual trust and learning together (than without).

13 Limitations

With regard to the research methodological approach, it should be noted for the interpretation of the results that the sample and the learning locations in the company and VET school have a strong regional concentration. All institutions are regionally limited to one location in Germany. Consequently, it remains unclear whether or to what extent the findings generated here can be transferred to the European context. It is therefore not possible to generalize the findings.

It should also be noted that the results generated do not apply to all individuals or were identified equally in all investigation groups. Although a large part of the participants could benefit from peer learning, not all apprentices could benefit to the same degree. Another limitation is the lack of a follow-up survey; therefore, no long-term results can be reported.

For the interpretation, it is also limiting to consider that there are further factors that can influence or explain the learning as well as the development of the dimensions measured here. Peer learning itself is only one influencing factor; in addition, other aspects of the private, company and school environment have an impact on the apprentices, which can potentially strengthen or reduce their learning and working behaviour.

Furthermore, the results of both the quantitative and qualitative surveys should be interpreted with caution, as they are based on self-reporting or self-assessment. Accordingly, effects or patterns of social desirability in response behaviour cannot be ruled out, and the same applies to the risk of apprentices overestimating themselves (in a positive sense) in the interviews.

In addition to these aspects, self-activation to participate in the interviews must also be mentioned, as there is the disadvantage of a selective sample (Reinders, 2005). While voluntariness can be assumed, at the same time there is a risk of disproportionately generating the more satisfied apprentices to participate in the interviews. Taking this idea further, negative or critical arguments about peer learning may be underrepresented. The same is likely to be evident in the interviews with teaching and instructing staff. Likewise, it should be noted that the six institutions also participated in the project voluntarily. This allows the thought that this could be a positive selection or relatively well-structured companies or VET schools.

14 Advice for the Practice in VET and Prospects

Based on the empirical data of the scientific analysis, practical implementation recommendations can and should be formulated. This includes how and under which conditions and requirements peer learning can be implemented in VET, in the learning locations company and VET school.

An important result of the interviews is the central importance of the temporal and structural organization because the framework conditions were described and evaluated very differently in the institutions. Fixed planned times and rooms are essential for the implementation of peer learning. Especially the temporal (annual) planning seemed to be particularly challenging

for some companies and schools. Consequently, early and long-term appointments are needed to determine in which time slots (or days) peer learning can be implemented. In such cases, (early) coordination with other departments (in the company) or class grades or year groups (in the VET schools) are key aspects.

In addition, it should be considered whether it might be useful, especially in larger groups or school classes, to start with peer tutoring and then carry out peer education. Peer tutoring allows for collaboration with varying partners from the class group and can contribute to social integration and awareness of collaborative learning through the changing constellations of people. Peer tutoring would allow all group members and all apprentices to experience the role of a teacher through the tandem constellation. Thus, this role (or task) can potentially be better understood, and the subsequent implementation of peer education can maybe better realise.

15 Conclusion and Prospects

The presented project contributes to the knowledge about the effects of cooperative learning activities of apprentices in VET. The results indicate an increasing interest of the apprentices in working together with other apprentices, and they reported new friendships. Furthermore, they express the intention to ask each other for advice in the future and to support each other with positive feedback. It was also reported in the interviews that peer learning could contribute to the development of a new feedback culture in the classes and learning groups. In addition, peer learning was able to promote social integration and solidarity.

Nevertheless, it remains unclear for which group of people peer learning is particularly suitable and how peer learning can be effectively designed for all. The analysis shows that peer learning enables positive effects and developments for a part of the apprentices but not for the whole group. Accordingly, with regard to the practical implementation of peer learning, it should be determined once again how the interventions can be designed in a more individualized and subject-oriented way so that a larger part of the group (or preferably all) can be addressed and can benefit in their development through peer learning. Initial considerations for further individualization are associated with the use of peer tutoring since this peer approach is carried out in the entire class group, all group members are actively involved, and the learning pace in the tandems can be set individually in each case.

In summary, it can be concluded that the use of peer learning for the design of learning situations (especially in the repetition and consolidation of previously taught content and topics) in VET should be examined on a situational basis and implemented accordingly. Teachers and instructors could potentially be relieved of time, and the learning processes could be made more active, attractive and varied.

In conclusion, it should be noted that there is still a need for research, so with regard to a scientific perspective, the findings generated here should first be reviewed in a further study. Moreover, potentially relevant (new) findings could be generated by subgroup comparisons that include personal characteristics, such as a comparison of genders, ages, school-leaving certification, learning institutions or professions. In addition to the research desiderata listed, an adaptation of the approaches to other professions (e.g. commercial-administrative) should be focussed.

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